

Uranium Chelates of Some Substituted 8-Hydroxy Quinoline-7-Sulfonic Acids. Uranium (VI)-5-Chloro-8-Hydroxy Quinoline-7-Sulfonic Acid Chelate – a Spectrophotometric Study

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Uranium (VI) forms in aqueous medium an orange red complex with 5-chloro 8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid, stable in the pH range 5 to 6.5. The composition of the complex is $\text{UO}_2(\text{CHQS})_2$ (where CHQS is the ligand). The stability constant of the complex was found to be $\log K = 8.4 \pm 0.05$ and the free energy of the formation was found to be $\Delta F^\circ = -11.5 \pm 0.02$ at 25°. The effect of ionic strength, presence of foreign ions, thermodynamic functions as entropy and enthalpy changes on the formation of the complex have been investigated.

The ability of 5-chloro-8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid to form metal chelates is due to the periposition of the phenolic hydroxyl group to the hetero atom nitrogen, forming a grouping N-C-C-O which can give rise to a formation of five-membered ring with the metal ion like its parent compound 8-quinolinol. In a recent communication from this laboratory Banerji and Srivastava¹ reported the preparation of this compound and its colour reactions with various metal ions. The present communication deals with the study of the formation of the beautiful orange red complex between hexavalent uranium and 5-chloro-8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid regarding the composition, structure and stability by spectrophotometric methods in aqueous medium.

EXPERIMENTAL AND RESULTS

Standard solution of uranium was prepared by dissolving Uranyl Nitrate (A.R.) in double distilled water. A purified sample of sodium salt 8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid was used for the preparation of stock solution in aqueous medium. Hydrogen ion concentrations were adjusted with sodium-acetate-acetic acid buffer. Stock solutions of diverse ions were prepared from the nitrate or chloride of the corresponding metal.

Spectrophotometric measurements were made on a Hilger Uvispec Spectrophotometer (Model H 700-308), equipped with thermoplates to stabilise the temperature of the cell holder, using glass cells of one cm light path. pH measurements were made with the help of a Beckman pH meter (Model H2).

Absorption spectra of the complex: To an aliquot quantity of the uranium solution ($4 \times 10^{-4}M$), taken in 25 ml flask, the reagent ($1 \times 10^{-4}M$) solution was added and the volume was finally made to 25 ml after adjusting the pH to 5.8. A reagent solution was also prepared under similar condition. The absorbance of the orange red chelate has been measured

against water blank. Fig. 1 shows that the absorbance of the reagent and the coloured solution decreases gradually as wavelength increases; but from 470 $m\mu$ to higher wavelength, the absorbance of the reagent is negligible. Therefore all colour measurements were done at 470 $m\mu$.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of uranium-5-chloro-8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid chelate (Curve 1) and reagent alone (Curve 2).

Effect of pH on the chelate: Solutions containing uranyl nitrate and the reagent (4×10^{-4} and $1 \times 10^{-4} M$) were prepared at different hydrogen ion concentrations and the absorbance at various wavelengths were taken. The complex was found to be stable in the pH range 5 to 6.5, and for subsequent studies pH 5.8 was selected since the complex developed maximum colour intensity at this pH. Colour formation was found to be instantaneous and it was observed that even up to 48 hr there was no change in absorbance values. Temperature change had little effect on the colour formation when the ligand is present in excess.

Nature of the Complex in solution

Job's method of continuous variation: Job's method of continuous variation² as modified by Vosburg and Cooper³ was employed for determining the molar composition of the complex in solution. Optical densities of the three sets of solutions by mixing the components ($12 \times 10^{-4} M$, $8 \times 10^{-4} M$, $6 \times 10^{-4} M$) were determined at 470 $m\mu$ after adjusting the pH in all cases to 5.8. The absorbance values were plotted against the ratio metal/metal+reagent, in which the peaks in the curves occur when the molar ratio of uranium (VI) to 5-chloro-8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid is 1 : 2 in all cases.

Slope-ratio method: The molar composition of uranium-5-chloro-8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid chelate was also determined by the method developed by Harvey and Manning⁴. For this purpose two series of solutions were prepared employing $1 \times 10^{-3} M$

2. P. Job, *Annals. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113,(10).

3. W. C. Vosburg and G. R. Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 1630.

4. A. E. Harvey and D. L. Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.

solution of 5-chloro-8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid and uranyl nitrate. In one series the uranium concentration was varied (from 1 ml to 10 ml), maintaining the concentration of the reagent constant and in sufficient excess. In the other series the reagent concentration was varied in the similar way maintaining the metal ion concentration constant and in sufficient excess. The absorbance of the solutions of both these series were determined at $470\text{ m}\mu$ after making up the volume to 25 ml and adjusting the pH at 5.8. The values obtained were plotted and the slope of the two straight lines indicates that the molar ratio of uranium to reagent is 1 : 2.

Mole-ratio method : In the determination of empirical formula of the complex employing the mole-ratio method of Yoe and Jones⁵ a series of solutions were prepared from $4 \times 10^{-4}M$ and $2 \times 10^{-4}M$ of the metal ion and equimolar solutions of the reagent in such a way that the molar ratio of the metal ion to the reagent was varied from 1 : 0.5 to 1 : 5. The results when plotted show a break at the ratio metal to reagent is 1 : 2, indicating that the composition of the complex is 1 : 2, which confirms the results obtained by using Job's method and slope-ratio method.

Uranium (VI) ions in solutions exist as UO_2^{+2} . The findings show that a stable complex is formed in solution between one mole of uranium and two moles of 5-chloro-8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid. Consequently the following tentative structure is postulated.

Evaluation of stability constant : For the purpose of the determination of stability constant of the complex calculations have been made from the optical density data by the method of Banerji and Dey⁶ and the mole-ratio method of Yoe and Jones⁵. The values obtained from these methods have been found to be in close agreement and $\log K$ in the system uranium-5-chloro-8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid chelate works out to be 8.4 ± 0.05 and the free energy of formation ΔF° , calculated according to Van't Hoff isotherm, was found to be $= -11.5 \pm 0.02$ k.cal/mole at 25° .

Effect of diverse ions : In the optical density measurements of the orange red coloured uranium chelate in aqueous medium, foreign ions like oxalate, iron, cerium, thorium, titanium, vanadium, zirconium and molybdenum were found to interfere even when present in minute quantities. Large quantities of acetate, borate, chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate, nickel, cobalt manganese, lanthanum and beryllium had no effect.

Entropy and Enthalpy changes : In view of obtaining the thermodynamic stability constant, we have determined the entropy and enthalpy using Gibbs-Helmholtz equation and

5. J. Yoe and A. Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem. analyt. Edn.*, 1944, **111**, 16.

6. S. K. Banerji and A. K. Dey, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1961, **179**, 30.

temperature coefficient method at pH 5.8 and ionic strength 0.02. The stability constant and free energy of formation of the complex at various temperatures are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

log K at various temperatures (ionic strength 0.02, pH 5.8)

T	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°
log K	8.4	8.47	8.50	8.52	8.9
F° k.cal/mole	-11.51	-11.77	-12.07	-12.27	-12.99

From the slope of the curve obtained by plotting log K against $1/T$, (Fig. 2) ΔH of the reaction has been calculated and found to be -4.1 k.cal/mole. Assuming this to be constant over a range of experimental temperatures ΔS of the reaction has been calculated and found to be 52.3 e.u.

Fig. 2. Variation of log K with $1/T$.

The study of stability constant at various ionic strength indicate that the stability constant decreases with an increase in the ionic strength as expected, but beyond ionic strength 0.3 the values of K remains almost constant. This is probably due to the fact that the activity coefficient of an ion passes through the minimum as the ionic strength increases.

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